

DIOPHANTINE EQUATIONS COMING FROM BINOMIAL NEAR-COLLISIONS

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Abstract

In this paper we solve the diophantine equation $\binom{m}{l} - \binom{n}{k} = d$ (where m, n are positive integer unknowns) when $(k, l) = (6, 3), (3, 6)$ for various values of d and when $(k, l) = (8, 2)$ and $d = 1$. As a byproduct of our results we will obtain that (k, l) -near collisions with difference 1 do not exist if $(k, l) = (3, 6), (8, 2)$, thus establishing a conjecture stated in the article published in 2017 by Blokhuis, Brouwer and de Weger.

1. Introduction

The quadruple (n, k, l, m) is said to be a *(binomial) near collision with difference d* if there exists a pair (m, n) of integers with $2 \leq k \leq n/2$, $2 \leq l \leq m/2$, such that $\binom{m}{l} - \binom{n}{k} = d$ and $\binom{m}{l} \geq d^3$. Note that the above restrictions on k, l are very natural in view of the symmetries $\binom{m}{l} = \binom{m}{m-l}$ and $\binom{n}{k} = \binom{n}{n-k}$.

If we consider $k, l \geq 2$ and $d \neq 0$ (not-necessarily positive) as given fixed integers with $k \neq l$, we obtain the Diophantine equation

$$\binom{m}{l} - \binom{n}{k} = d, \tag{1}$$

in the positive integer unknowns m, n , without any restriction on the size of $\binom{m}{l}$ compared to d . In Section 2 we will solve (1) when $(k, l) = (3, 6)$ and $d = \pm 1$, and in Section 3 we will solve (1) with $(k, l) = (8, 2)$ and $d = 1$. Our main results, Theorems 2.2, 2.4, 3.1 respectively imply Corollaries 2.3, 2.5, 3.2. As a consequence we have that *(k, l) -near collisions with difference 1 do not exist if $(k, l) \in \{(6, 3), (3, 6), (8, 2)\}$* , thus establishing certain cases of Conjecture 2 in [1].

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We now sketch the method for solving the equations mentioned above, which we apply in Sections 2 and 3 . For each equation we work as follows. We reduce its resolution to the problem of finding the points (u, v) with integral coordinates on a certain elliptic curve C whose equation is not in Weierstrass form. We find a Weierstrass model E and an explicit birational transformation

$$C \ni (u, v) \longrightarrow (x, y) = (\mathcal{X}(u, v), \mathcal{Y}(u, v)) \in E$$

$$C \ni (\mathcal{U}(x, y), \mathcal{V}(x, y)) = (u, v) \longleftarrow (x, y) \in E$$

between C and E . This is accomplished by the MAPLE implementation of van Hoeij’s algorithm [6]. The typical point on C is denoted by P^C and the corresponding point on E via the above birational transformation by P^E . We will also use the notation $(u(P), v(P))$ for the coordinates of the point P viewed as a point on C , hence $(u(P), v(P)) = P^C$, and $(x(P), y(P))$ for the coordinates of the point P viewed as a point on E , hence $(x(P), y(P)) = P^E$. Thus, if $P^C = (u, v) = (u(P), v(P))$ and $P^E = (x, y) = (x(P), y(P))$, then $x = \mathcal{X}(u, v)$, $y = \mathcal{Y}(u, v)$ and $u = \mathcal{U}(x, y)$, $v = \mathcal{V}(x, y)$.

Our problem is reduced to the following:

To compute explicitly all points $P^E \in E(\mathbb{Q})$ such that $P^C \in C(\mathbb{Z})$.

We deal with this problem as follows. Using the routine `MordellWeilBasis` of MAGMA[2] based on the work of many contributors, like J. Cremona, S. Donnelly, T. Fisher, M. Stoll, to mention a few of them, we compute a Mordell-Weil basis for $E(\mathbb{Q})$ and let P_1^E, \dots, P_r^E be generators of the free part of $E(\mathbb{Q})$. In certain cases, especially when the rank of the elliptic curve is ≥ 5 , it is necessary to improve the Mordell-Weil basis computed by MAGMA, in the sense of the Remark at the end of Section 2; see also the “Important computational issue” of [7]; we will need to do this in both Sections 2 and 3. Let $P^C = (u, v)$ denote the typical unknown point with integral coordinates. Its transformed point P^E via the previously mentioned birational transformation is a point with rational coordinates, therefore $P^E = m_1 P_1^E + \dots + m_r P_r^E + T^E$, where m_1, \dots, m_r are unknown integers and T^E denotes the typical torsion point (only finitely many and, actually, very few options for T^E exist). To this we associate the linear form

$$L(P) = (m_0 + \frac{s}{t})\omega_1 + m_1\mathfrak{l}(P_1) + \dots + m_r\mathfrak{l}(P_r) \{\pm\mathfrak{l}(P_0)\}. \tag{2}$$

Some explanations are in place here. Firstly, \mathfrak{l} denotes the map $\mathfrak{l} : E(\mathbb{R}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}/\mathbb{Z}\omega_1$, closely related to the elliptic-logarithm function, which is defined and discussed in detail in Chapter 3 of [14], especially, Theorem 3.5.2. Next, ω_1 is the minimal positive real period of E , m_0 is an extra integer whose size depends explicitly on $M := \max_{1 \leq i \leq r} |m_i|$, and s, t are relatively prime integers as follows: $t \geq 1$ divides the lcm of the orders of the non-zero torsion points of E and s is such that

$-1/2 < s/t \leq 1/2$.² Last, the indication $\{\}$ in the summand $\pm l(P_0)$ means that this is present only in Section 2, where P_0 is a certain explicitly known point. The *Elliptic Logarithm Method* exploits the fact that u, v are integers in order to find an upper bound for $|L(P)|$ in terms of M (see (17)) and, on the other hand, applies a deep result of S. David [3] in order to obtain a lower bound for $|L(P)|$ in terms of M . Comparing the two bounds of $|L(P)|$ we obtain the relation

$$\rho M^2 \leq \frac{c_{11}c_{13}}{2\theta}(\log(\alpha M + \beta) + c_{14})(\log \log(\alpha M + \beta) + c_{15})^{r+3} + \gamma + \frac{c_{11}}{2\theta} \log \frac{c_9}{1 + \theta} + \frac{1}{2}c_{10}, \tag{3}$$

where all constants involved in it are explicit; see relation (9.8), Theorem 9.1.3 of [14]. It is clear that, if M is larger than an explicit bound B , then the left-hand side is *larger* than the right-hand side and this contradiction certainly implies that $M \leq B$. Since B is explicit, this allows us to compute all integer points $P^C = (u, v)$ as follows: for each (m_1, \dots, m_r) in the range $|m_i| \leq M$ ($i = 1, \dots, r$) we compute each point $P^E = m_1P_1^E + \dots + m_rP_r^E + T^E$ with T^E a torsion point and then we compute its transformed point P^C via the previously mentioned birational transformation; if P^C has integer coordinates, then we have gotten an integer point $P^C = (u, v)$.

In principle, this procedure allows to pick-up all integer points (u, v) and, indeed, this is so if the bound B is small, say around 30. But the bound obtained from (3) is huge and we must reduce it to a manageable size. This is accomplished with de Weger’s [15] technique, the basic tool of which is the *LLL-algorithm* of Lenstra-Lenstra-Lovász [5]. The *reduction process* appropriate for our purpose is described in Chapter 10 of [14].

2. Equation (1) with $(k, l) = (3, 6)$ and $d = \pm 1$

Replacing in (1) d by $-d$, we obtain the equation

$$\binom{n}{3} = \binom{m}{6} + d, \tag{4}$$

which we study in this section. Putting $u := n - 1$ and $v := (m - 2)(m - 3)/2$, we have

$$\binom{n}{3} = \frac{1}{6}((u + 1)u(u - 1)), \quad \binom{m}{6} = \frac{(v - 3)(v - 1)v}{6 \cdot 5 \cdot 3},$$

so that equation (4) implies

$$15(u^3 - u - 6d) = v^3 - 4v^2 + 3v. \tag{5}$$

²Note that, by a famous theorem of B. Mazur, $11 \neq t \leq 12$; see [8], [9], or Theorem 7.5 of [11].

We rewrite equation (5) as $g(u, v) = 0$, where

$$g(u, v) = 15u^3 - v^3 + 4v^2 - 90d - 15u - 3v. \tag{6}$$

In case that $d = (N^3 - N)/6$, where N is an explicitly known non-zero integer, it is shown in [7] how the method of Chapter 8 of [14] can be applied in order to compute –at least in principle– all integer solutions of (6). A rough description of the above mentioned method is as follows: The curve $C : g(u, v) = 0$, being a non-singular cubic, has genus one. Moreover, $(u, v) = (n, 1)$ is a rational point of C , so that C is a model of an elliptic curve over \mathbb{Q} . The MAPLE implementation of van Hoeij’s algorithm [6] gives the birational transformation between C and the Weierstrass model

$$E : y^2 = x^3 - 1575x + A(N) \tag{7}$$

$$A(N) := 33750N^3 - 33750N - \frac{1366875}{4}N^6 + \frac{1366875}{2}N^4 - \frac{1366875}{4}N^2 + 52650.$$

The birational transformation between C to E mentioned in page 2, as well as all other “technical” information is exposed in detail in [7]. As a result, the following theorem is the specialization of (3) in our present situation.

Theorem 2.1. *If $|u(P)| \geq 3|N|$, then either $M \leq c_{12}$ or*

$$\rho M^2 \leq c_{13}(\log(\alpha M + \beta) + c_{14})(\log \log(\alpha M + \beta) + c_{15})^{r+3} + \gamma + \log 0.085 + \frac{1}{2} \log(200|N|^3),$$

where r is the rank of the elliptic curve (7), $\rho (> 0)$ is the least eigenvalue of the (positive-definite) height-pairing matrix of the Mordell-Weil basis which we have computed for that elliptic curve, and all other constants involved in the above relation depend on N , are positive and can be explicitly calculated.

Remark. According to the end of Section 1, Theorem 2.1 implies an explicit bound of M . Moreover, it is not difficult to see that the resulting upper bound is a *decreasing function* of ρ . In Section 2 and more importantly in Section 3, the value of ρ plays a crucial role when we apply the reduction process described in Chapter 10 of [14]. More specifically, the reduced upper bound given by the relation (10.5) in that reference, heavily depends on a parameter κ_4 which is a positive multiple of ρ : the larger ρ (hence also κ_4) is, the smaller is the reduced upper bound. Therefore, if the value of ρ resulting from a certain Mordell-Weil basis \mathcal{B}_2 is larger than the value of ρ resulting from another basis \mathcal{B}_1 , we consider \mathcal{B}_2 as a *better basis* than \mathcal{B}_1 for the application of the Elliptic Logarithm Method. The method which we apply in this paper in order to obtain a better Mordell-Weil basis starting from a given one, is exposed in [12]; see also [4] for another interesting approach to computing better (in the above sense) Mordell-Weil bases.

Of special interest are the cases $N = \mp 2$ for which $d = (N^3 - N)/6 = \mp 1$, so that equation (4) becomes, respectively, a (3, 6) and (6, 3) near-collision with difference

1; these are two of the three unsolved collision problems in [1] which we manage to solve here; see Corollaries 2.3 and 2.5.

The case $d = -1$ is the most difficult one, and therefore we discuss it in some detail. Now our elliptic curve C becomes (cf. (6))

$$C : g(u, v) = 0, \quad \text{where } g(u, v) = 15u^3 - v^3 + 4v^2 - 15u - 3v + 90 \quad (8)$$

and its birationally equivalent Weierstrass model (7) is

$$E : y^2 = x^3 - 1575x - 12451725 =: f(x). \quad (9)$$

The Mordell-Weil group $E(\mathbb{Q})$ of rational points of the elliptic curve E has rank 5 (in the notation of Theorem 2.1, $r = 5$) and trivial torsion subgroup (in subsequent notation $r_0 = 1$). The free part of $E(\mathbb{Q})$ is generated by the points

$$P_1^E = (235, 395), \quad P_2^E = (615, 14805), \quad P_3^E = (3055, 168805),$$

$$P_4^E = (1350, 49455), \quad P_5^E = \left(\frac{1185}{4}, -\frac{28935}{8} \right).$$

Actually, the Mordell-Weil basis formed by the above five points is an improvement of the Mordell-Weil basis furnished by MAGMA, in the sense of the above Remark; see also the Remark immediately after Corollary 2.3.

The birational transformation between the models C and E is:

$$\mathcal{X}(u, v) = \frac{3(40u^2 + 55uv + v^2 - 60u + 106v - 277)}{(u + 2)^2}$$

$$\mathcal{Y}(u, v) = \frac{3(2505u^3 + 90u^2v + 220uv^2 + 5595u^2 - 685uv + 437v^2 - 6360u - 1718v - 15069)}{(u + 2)^3},$$

and

$$\mathcal{U}(x, y) = \frac{2x^3 - 60x^2 + 3xy - 49455x + 26865y + 68298525}{-x^3 + 360x^2 - 20925x + 66442950} \quad (10)$$

$$\mathcal{V}(x, y) = \frac{15(18x^2 + 11xy + 80325x - 1311y + 8004285)}{-x^3 + 360x^2 - 20925x + 66442950}$$

The linear form (2) is now

$$L(P) = \left(m_0 + \frac{s}{t} \right) \omega_1 + m_1 l(P_1) + m_2 l(P_2) + m_3 l(P_3) + m_4 l(P_4) + m_5 l(P_5) \pm l(P_0),$$

where

$$P_0^E = (3\zeta^2 + 165\zeta + 120, 660\zeta^2 + 270\zeta + 7515),$$

and ζ is the cubic root of 15.

Since $f(X)$ has only one real root, namely $e_1 \approx 234.0452973361$, we have $E(\mathbb{R}) = E_0(\mathbb{R})$ (= the unbounded component of E/\mathbb{R}) and therefore $l(P_i)$ coincides with the elliptic logarithm of P_i^E for $i = 1, \dots, 5$ (see Chapter 3 of [14], especially Theorem 3.5.2). On the other hand, P_0^E has irrational coordinates. As MAGMA does not possess a routine for calculating elliptic logarithms of non-rational points, we wrote our own routine in MAPLE for computing l -values of points with algebraic coordinates. The six points P_i^E , $i = 0, 1, \dots, 5$, are \mathbb{Z} -linearly independent because their regulator is non-zero (see Theorem 8.1 in [10]). Therefore our linear form $L(P)$ falls under the scope of the second “bullet” on page 99 of [14] and we have $r_0 = 1$, $s/t = s_0/t_0 = 0/1 = 0$, $d = 1$, $r = 5$, $n_i = m_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, 4$, $n_5 = \pm 1$, $n_0 = m_0$, $k = r + 1 = 6$, $\eta = 1$ and $N = \max_{0 \leq i \leq 5} |n_i| \leq r_0 \max\{M, \frac{1}{2}rM + 1\} + \frac{1}{2}\eta r_0 = \frac{5}{2}M + \frac{3}{2}$, so that, in the relation (9.6) of [14] we can take

$$\alpha = 5/2, \beta = 3/2. \tag{11}$$

We compute the canonical heights of $P_1^E, P_2^E, P_3^E, P_4^E, P_5^E$ using MAGMA.³ The corresponding height-pairing matrix \mathcal{H} has minimum eigenvalue

$$\rho \approx 0.7722274789. \tag{12}$$

Next we apply Proposition 2.6.3 of [14] in order to compute a positive constant γ with the property that $\hat{h}(P^E) - \frac{1}{2}h(x(P)) \leq \gamma$ for every point $P^E = (x(P), y(P)) \in E(\mathbb{Q})$, where h denotes Weil height;⁴ it turns out that

$$\gamma \approx 4.6451703657. \tag{13}$$

Note that the constants in (11), (12) and (13) appear in the inequality of Theorem 2.1. Further, we have to specify the constants $c_{12}, c_{13}, c_{14}, c_{15}$ defined in Theorem 9.1.2 of [14]. This is a rather straightforward task if one follows the detailed instructions of “Preparatory to Theorem 9.1.2” [14], which can be carried out even with a pocket calculator, except for the computation of various canonical heights. At this point we need to compute also the canonical height of the point P_0^E . Since this point has irrational coordinates we confine ourselves to the upper bound $\hat{h}(P_0^E) \leq 7.300572483$ proved in [7]. Carrying out all these computations is quite a boring job; fortunately, it can be performed almost automatically with a MAPLE program. In this way we compute

$$c_{12} \approx 1.210103 \cdot 10^{27}, \quad c_{13} \approx 1.342820 \cdot 10^{281}, \quad c_{14} \approx 2.09861, \quad c_{15} \approx 25.03975. \tag{14}$$

³For the definition of the canonical height we follow J.H. Silverman; as a consequence the values displayed here for the canonical heights are the halves of those computed by MAGMA and the least eigenvalue ρ of the height-pairing matrix \mathcal{H} below, is half of that computed by MAGMA; cf. “Warning” at bottom of p. 106 in [14].

⁴In the notation of that Proposition, as a curve D we take the minimal model of E , which is E itself.

Now, in view of Theorem 2.1 and (11), (12), (13), (14), we conclude that, if $|u(P)| \geq 6$, then either $M \leq c_{12}$ or

$$0.77222 \cdot M^2 \leq 1.34 \cdot 10^{281} \times (\log(2.5M + 1.5) + 2.0986) \times (\log(0.4342 \log(2.5M + 1.5)) + 25.0397)^5 + 5.4159.$$

But for all $M \geq 6.86 \cdot 10^{147}$, we check that the left-hand side is strictly larger than the right-hand side, which implies that $M < 6.86 \cdot 10^{147}$. Therefore,

$$|u(P)| \geq 6 \text{ implies } M \leq \max\{c_{12}, 6.86 \cdot 10^{147}\} = 6.86 \cdot 10^{147}. \tag{15}$$

An easy straightforward computation shows that all integer points P^C with $|u(P)| \leq 5$ (equivalently, all integer solutions (u, v) of (8) with $|u| \leq 5$) are the following:

$$P^C = (-2, 0), (-2, 1), (-2, 3), (-1, 6), (0, 6), (1, 6). \tag{16}$$

In order to find explicitly all points P^C with $|u(P)| \geq 6$ it is necessary to reduce the huge upper bound (15) to an upper bound of manageable size. This is accomplished in [7] using standard LLL-reduction; as a result it is shown that $M \leq 27$. Therefore, we have to check which points

$$P^E = m_1P_1^E + m_2P_2^E + m_3P_3^E + m_4P_4^E + m_5P_5^E, \text{ with } \max_{1 \leq i \leq 5} |m_i| \leq 27,$$

have the property that $P^E = (x, y)$ maps via the transformation (10) to a point $P^C = (u, v) \in C$ with integer coordinates. We remark here that every point P^C with $u(P)$ integer and $|u(P)| \geq 6$ is obtained in this way, but the converse is not necessarily true, i.e. if $\max_{1 \leq i \leq 5} |m_i| \leq 27$ and the above P^E maps to P^C with integer coordinates, it is not necessarily true that $|u(P)| \geq 6$.

If we were going to check all 5-tuples $(m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4, m_5)$ in the range $-27 \leq m_i \leq 27$ by “brute force” this would take more than 15 days of computation. Therefore, we apply a simple but very effective trick to speed up this final search. This trick, called in [12] *inequality trick*, is based on the observation that, for every 5-tuple $(m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4, m_5)$ corresponding to a point $P^E = m_1P_1^E + m_2P_2^E + m_3P_3^E + m_4P_4^E + m_5P_5^E$, the upper bound of $|L(P)|$ mentioned just above (3), more specifically,

$$|L(P)| \leq k_1 \exp(k_2 - k_4M^2) \tag{17}$$

must be satisfied for the six-tuple (m_0, m_1, \dots, m_5) , where m_0 is the extra parameter appearing in (2) with $|m_0| \leq 27$. The heuristic observation is that the above inequality is very unlikely to be satisfied by points P^E with at least one large coefficient m_i . The reason is that the elliptic logarithms $\ell(P_i)$ are more or less randomly distributed (at least there is no reason to assume otherwise) so that the linear $L(P)$ is rarely very small. Checking whether the $L(P)$, coming from a certain 6-tuple $(m_0, m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4, m_5)$ in the range $-27 \leq m_i \leq 27$, satisfies the above displayed inequality requires real number computations which are considerably faster than those required for computing symbolically $P^E = m_1P_1^E + m_2P_2^E + m_3P_3^E + m_4P_4^E + m_5P_5^E$ and then checking whether the corresponding point P^C is integral. Actually, this reduces the computation to a few hours and furnishes us with the points figuring in Table 1.

m_1	m_2	m_3	m_4	m_5	$P^E = (x, y)$	$P^C = (u, v)$
-1	0	0	-1	1	(27075, -4455045)	(-2, 1)
-1	0	0	0	0	(235, -395)	(1, 6)
0	0	-1	-1	0	(495, -10395)	(-1, 6)
0	0	-1	0	-1	(555, 12555)	(-138, -339)
0	0	-1	0	0	(3055, -168805)	(-2, 3)
0	0	0	0	1	(1185/4, -28935/8)	(0, 6)

Table 1: All points $P^E = \sum_i m_i P_i^E$ with $P^C = (u, v) \in \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$.

Only the point P^C which corresponds to $(m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4, m_5) = (0, 0, -1, 0, -1)$ has $|u(P)| \geq 6$. The remaining five points $P^C = (u, v)$ satisfy $|u| < 6$ and therefore they are contained in the already found list of points (16). This list contains one more point, namely $(u, v) = (-2, 0)$, which is not among the points of the above table, because it does not correspond to a point P^E via the (affine) birational transformation of page 5. We have thus proved the following.

Theorem 2.2. *The integer solutions of the equation (8) are*

$$(u, v) = (-138, -339), (-2, 0), (-2, 1), (-2, 3), (-1, 6), (0, 6), (1, 6).$$

Corollary 2.3. *No (3, 6) near-collision with difference 1 exists.*

Proof. Assume that $(n, 3, m, 6)$ is a near collision with difference 1. Then $\binom{m}{6} - \binom{n}{3} = 1$, which is equation (4) with $d = -1$. At the beginning of Section 2 we saw that, if we put $u = n - 1$ and $v = (m - 2)(m - 3)/2$, then (u, v) is an integer solution of the equation (5) with $d = -1$, i.e. (u, v) is an integral point on the curve (8). By the restrictions on the definition of collision, $n \geq 6$, so $u \geq 7$ and by Theorem 2.2, no solution (u, v) to (8) exists with $u \geq 7$. \square

Remark. As mentioned below (9), the online MAGMA calculator (v2.24-3) returns a different Mordell-Weil basis for the elliptic curve (9). The value of ρ corresponding to that basis is $\rho \approx 0.410937$. As a consequence, the initial upper bound for M (cf. (15)) is $M < 6.86 \cdot 10^{147}$ and after four reduction steps, the final reduced upper bound is 34. Therefore the final check for all 6-tuples (m_0, m_1, \dots, m_5) in the range $-34 \leq m_i \leq 34$ needs at least four times ($4 \approx (34/27)^6$) more computation time; actually, according to our experiments, it needs much more.

The case $d = 1$ is treated in a way completely analogous to that of case $d = -1$.⁵ Now our curve is $C : 15u^3 - v^3 + 4v^2 - 15u - 3v - 90 = 0$ and the birationally equivalent Weierstrass model E is, by (7), $E : y^2 = x^3 - 1575x - 12046725$. All computations are *much simpler* because E has rank $r = 2$, and $P_1 = (26745/4, -4373685/8), P_2 = (2995, 163855)$ is a Mordell-Weil basis. As a result we have the following.

⁵More details in [7].

Theorem 2.4. *The only integer solution of the equation $15u^3 - v^3 + 4v^2 - 15u - 3v - 90 = 0$ is $(u, v) = (2, 3)$.*

Corollary 2.5. *No $(6, 3)$ near-collision with difference 1 exists.*

Proof. Assume that $(n, 6, m, 3)$ is a near collision with difference 1. Then $\binom{m}{3} - \binom{n}{6} = 1$ and, on interchanging m, n , we are led to equation (4) with $d = 1$. According to Section 2, if in (4) we put $u = n - 1$ and $v = (m - 2)(m - 3)/2$, then (u, v) is an integer solution of the equation (5) with $d = 1$. Moreover, by the restrictions on the definition of collision, $n \geq 6$, so $u \geq 7$. According to Theorem 2.4, the only solution is $(u, v) = (2, 3)$, and this concludes the proof. \square

3. Equation (1) with $(k, l) = (8, 2)$ and $d = 1$

We write our equation as follows:

$$\frac{(n^2 - 7n)(n^2 - 7n + 6)(n^2 - 7n + 10)(n^2 - 7n + 12)}{3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 \cdot 7 \cdot 8} + 2 = (m^2 - m).$$

Putting

$$u = \frac{1}{2}n^2 - \frac{7}{2}n + 6, \quad v = 210m - 105, \tag{18}$$

we are led to

$$v^2 = 35u^4 - 350u^3 + 945u^2 - 630u + 315^2, \tag{19}$$

hence, it suffices to explicitly solve equation (19). The most straightforward thing for doing this, would be to turn to MAGMA’s routine `IntegralQuarticPoints`, which is based on [13] and was firstly developed in 1999 by Emmanuel Herrmann and further improved in the years 2006-2013 by Stephen Donnelly and other people of MAGMA group. Indeed, we ran the above routine for (19) on a computer Intel i5-7200U @ 2.50GHz, but after five days, MAGMA gave up without results, with the message “Killed”. Consequently we had to solve (19) “non-automatically”, following the method of [13], as exposed in Chapter 6 of [14]. For the successful accomplishment of this, crucial role play:

1. Our Mordell-Weil basis, which is an improvement of the one computed by MAGMA, as explained in the Remark at the end of this section.
2. The application of an *inequality trick* completely analogous to that which we start discussing a few lines above (17).

We will deal with the elliptic curve

$$C : v^2 = Q(u) := 35u^4 - 350u^3 + 945u^2 - 630u + 315^2.$$

We use the notation, results etc of Chapter 6 of [14]; thus we have $a = 35$, $b = -350$, $c = 945$, $d = -630$, $e = 315$. By relation (6.3) in [14] the Weierstrass model which is birationally equivalent to the curve C is

$$E : y^2 = f(x) := x^3 + Ax + B, \tag{20}$$

where $A = -13968675$ and $B = 3410363250$, and the birational functions

$$\begin{aligned} C \ni (u, v) &\mapsto (\mathcal{X}(u, v), \mathcal{Y}(u, v)) = (x, y) \in E \\ E \ni (x, y) &\mapsto (\mathcal{U}(x, y), \mathcal{V}(x, y)) = (u, v) \in C \end{aligned}$$

are

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{X}(u, v) &= \frac{315(u^2 - 2u - 2v + 630)}{u^2} \\ \mathcal{Y}(u, v) &= -\frac{630(175u^3 - 945u^2 - uv + 945u + 630v - 198450)}{u^3} \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

(relation (6.4) in [14]) and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}(x, y) &= -\frac{630(x + y + 109935)}{x^2 - 630x - 13792275} \\ \mathcal{V}(x, y) &= -315(x^4 + 630x^3 + 2x^2y - 529200x^2 + 439740xy + 22441718250x \\ &\quad - 110933550y - 196956864680625) : (x^2 - 630x - 13792275)^2 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

(relations (6.5) and (6.6) in [14]).

We have to calculate the three real roots $e_1 > e_2 > e_3$ of $f(x)$ and a fundamental pair of periods $\omega_1 \in \mathbb{R}$, $\omega_2 \in i\mathbb{R}$ for the Weierstrass \wp function which parametrizes E . Now we refer to Section 1, the notations of which we adopt here. The rank of E is 5 and the torsion subgroup $E_{tors}(\mathbb{Q})$ is trivial. The following points form a Mordell-Weil basis for $E(\mathbb{Q})$:⁶

$$\begin{aligned} P_1^E &= (-1799, 150724), P_2^E = (105, -44100), P_3^E = (-315, -88200), \\ P_4^E &= (8985, 776700), P_5^E = (3885, 88200). \end{aligned}$$

We note that, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, the points P_i^E belong to $E_1(\mathbb{R})$, the bounded component (“egg”) of $E(\mathbb{R})$ and therefore by “Conclusions and remarks” (1) in page 51 of [14], $\mathfrak{l}(P_i)$ is the elliptic logarithm of the point $P_i^E + Q_2^E$, where $Q_2^E = (e_2, 0)$. Now $P_i^E + Q_2^E$ belongs to the unbounded component $E_0(\mathbb{R})$ of $E(\mathbb{R})$, but its coordinates are non-rational, belonging to the cubic extension of $\mathbb{Q}(e_2)/\mathbb{Q}$. Therefore, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, $\mathfrak{l}(P_i)$ is equal to the elliptic logarithm of $P_i^E + Q_2^E$, which we compute using our MAPLE routine, mentioned a few lines above (11). The points P_4^E and P_5^E belong to $E_0(\mathbb{R})$ and therefore, for $i = 3, 4$, $\mathfrak{l}(P_i)$ is equal to the elliptic logarithm of P_i^E . Next we need to calculate approximate values of the canonical heights (cf. footnote 3), the height-pairing matrix \mathcal{H} and its minimum eigenvalue (cf. footnote 6)

$$\rho \approx 0.5764009469.$$

We compute a positive number γ such that $\hat{h}(P^E) - \frac{1}{2}h(x(P)) \leq \gamma$, where h denotes Weil height, by applying Proposition 2.6.3 of [14]. In the notation of that

⁶See the Remark at the end of this section.

proposition, as a curve D we take the minimal model of E , which is E itself, and following the simple instructions therein, we compute $\gamma = 6.4974558131$. Finally, in order to compute the constants involved in Theorem 9.1.2 of [14] that are necessary for the application of Theorem 9.1.3 of [14], we replace the pair of fundamental periods ω_1, ω_2 , for which $\tau := \omega_1/\omega_2$ does not belong to the fundamental region of the complex upper half-plane, by the pair $(\varpi_1, \varpi_2) = (\omega_2, -\omega_1)$; for this pair, $\tilde{\tau} := \varpi_1/\varpi_2$ satisfies $|\tilde{\tau}| \geq 1$, $\Im \tilde{\tau} > 0$ and $|\Re \tilde{\tau}| < 1/2$, hence it belongs to the fundamental region.

In order to obtain a relation of the form (3), we will apply Theorem 9.1.3 of [14]. That theorem applies to points $P^C = (u(P), v(P))$ with $|u(P)|$ sufficiently large. Table 6.1 in Chapter 6 of [14] indicates a procedure for computing how large $|u(P)|$ should be; actually, we must have $|u(P)| \geq \max\{u^{**}, \bar{u}^{**}\}$ and u^{**}, \bar{u}^{**} are calculated as explained in that table. The existence of two columns in Table 6.1 of Chapter 6 of [14] and in its specialization to our case, which is Table 2 below, is explained as follows: At this stage it is convenient, instead of searching for solutions of $Q(u) = v^2$ with $v \geq 0$ and u of whatever sign, to look for solutions of both equations $Q(u) = v^2$ and $\overline{Q}(u) := Q(-u) = v^2$ with $u, v \geq 0$. Thus, a “bar” over a constant refers to the second equation. The constant $\max\{c_7, \bar{c}_7\}$ (= 13 in our case) is used in the application of Theorem 9.1.3 of [14].

$Q(u) =$ $35u^4 - 350u^3 + 945u^2 - 630u + 99225$	$\overline{Q}(u) =$ $35u^4 + 350u^3 + 945u^2 + 630u + 99225$
$\sigma = 1$	$\bar{\sigma} = -1$
$x(u) = 315 \frac{u^2 - 2u + 630 + 2(Q(u))^{1/2}}{u^2}$	$\bar{x}(u) = 315 \frac{u^2 + 2u + 630 + 2(\overline{Q}(u))^{1/2}}{u^2}$
$u^{**} = 3$ and $c_7 = 13$	$\bar{u}^{**} = 80$ and $\bar{c}_7 = 13$
$P_0^E =$ $(630\sqrt{35} + 315, 110250 + 630\sqrt{35})$	$\bar{P}_0^E =$ $(630\sqrt{35} + 315, -110250 - 630\sqrt{35})$
$\iota(P_0)$	$\iota(\bar{P}_0) = -\iota(P_0)$
$L(P) = \iota(P) - \iota(P_0)$	$\bar{L}(P) = \iota(P) + \iota(P_0)$

Table 2: Parameters and auxiliary functions for the solution of the quartic elliptic equation according to the Table 6.1 in [14]

From Table 2 it follows that the conditions of Theorem 6.8 in [14], which are also necessary for the application of Theorem 9.1.3 in [14], are fulfilled for all points $P^C \in C(\mathbb{Z})$ with $v(P) > 0$ and $|u(P)| \geq 80$. A quick computer search shows that the only points in $P^C(\mathbb{Z})$ with $|u(P)| < 80$ are those points (u, v) listed in Table 3 with $|u| < 80$. From Table 2 it follows also that, on applying Theorem 9.1.3 of [14], we must take $c_7 = 13$ and $L(P) = \iota(P) \pm \iota(P_0)$. We have already computed approximations of the coefficients ω_1 and ℓ_i ($i = 1, \dots, 5$) of the linear form $\iota(P)$, and using our aforementioned MAPLE routine we also compute $\ell_0 :=$

$l(P_0) \approx -0.179410143$.

Using the routine `IsLinearlyIndependent` of MAGMA, we see that the points P_i^E ($i = 0, \dots, 5$) are \mathbb{Z} -linearly independent, so that we are in the situation described in the second “bullet”, page 99 in [14]. Therefore, the parameters in the linear form (9.2) of [14] are

$$k = r + 1 = 6, \quad d = 1, \quad r_0 = 1, \quad (n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4, n_5) = (m_1, m_2, m_3, m_4, m_5), \\ n_6 = \pm 1, \quad \ell_6 = \ell_0.$$

In the notation of relation (9.3) in [14] we have $N_0 = \frac{5}{2}M + \frac{3}{2}$, hence $(\alpha, \beta) = (5/2, 3/2)$.

In order to compute various constants involved in the upper bound for M furnished by Theorem 9.1.3 of [14], we also need to compute $\hat{h}(P_0^E)$. Since P_0 is not a rational point we confine ourselves to the reasonably good upper bound of its canonical height obtained from Proposition 2.6.4 of [14]. In the notation of that proposition we take as curve D our curve E and obtain the bound $\hat{h}(P_0^E) \leq 14.72$.

We see that the degree of the number field generated by the coordinates of all points P_i ($i = 0, \dots, 5$) is 6, hence, in the notation of “Preparatory to Theorem 9.1.2” of [14], $D = 6$. Following the instructions therein and Theorem 9.1.2 we compute

$$c_{12} = 6.76211752 \cdot 10^{30}, \quad c_{13} = 3.68566633 \cdot 10^{286}, \quad c_{14} = 2.79176, \quad c_{15} = 28.91$$

and, in the notation of Theorem 9.1.3 in [14], $c_{16} = 0.68$, $c_{17} = 1.832$, $c_{18} = 1$. By that theorem, which in our case is Theorem 2.1, either $M \leq c_{12}$, or $\mathcal{B}(M) > 0$, where $\mathcal{B}(M) = c_{18}c_{13}(\log(\alpha M + \beta) + c_{14})(\log \log(\alpha M + \beta) + c_{15})^{k+2} + \gamma + c_{18} \log c_{16} + c_{17} - \rho \cdot M^2$. Note that all parameters in $\mathcal{B}(M)$ have already been computed and are displayed in this and the previous pages. Now it is straightforward to check that, for $M \geq 6.28 \cdot 10^{150}$, we have $\mathcal{B}(M) < 0$, hence

$$M \leq \max\{c_{12}, 6.28 \cdot 10^{150}\} = 6.28 \cdot 10^{150}.$$

We are now in a situation completely similar to that after relation (16). This time the process for the reduction of the above upper bound of M is repeated three times, giving successively the upper bounds 170, 30 and 28; the last upper bound cannot be further reduced. Next, we check which points $P^E = m_1P_1^E + \dots + m_5P_5^E$ in the range $\max_{1 \leq i \leq m} |m_i| \leq 28$ correspond to a point P^C with integral coordinates, using the *inequality trick*, as explained in the last paragraph above Table 1. The computation on a computer Intel i5-7200U @ 2.50GHz took a little more than 70 hours of computation and the results are comprised in Table 3. In particular, we have the following.

Theorem 3.1. *All integer solutions of the equation (19) are those listed in the seventh column of Table 3.*

Remark. The online MAGMA calculator (V2.24-3) returns the following Mordell-Weil basis for the elliptic curve (20): $(19705/81, 3758300/729)$, $(14665/4, -307475/8)$,

(8985, -776700), (693805, -577896200), (28035, -4652550). Using this basis and the method of [12], we obtained the considerably better basis (in the sense of the “Remark” immediately after Theorem 2.1) displayed a few lines below (22). Indeed, as we have already seen, the value of ρ for the improved basis is ≈ 0.5764 , while the approximate value of ρ for the above displayed basis is 0.1284705. As a consequence, the initial upper bound for M is $M < 1.34 \cdot 10^{151}$. This is not essentially worse than the upper bound for M displayed a few lines above Theorem 3.1. *However*, after four reduction steps – and here ρ plays its important role – the reduced upper bound is 62 and cannot be further reduced (remember that the final reduced bound with the better basis is 28). Therefore, had we used the above Mordell-Weil basis, the final check for all 6-tuples (m_0, m_1, \dots, m_5) in the range $-62 \leq m_i \leq 62$ would require at least $(62/28)^6$ times more computation time, which amounts to *at least one year of computation time!*

m_1	m_2	m_3	m_4	m_5	$P^E = (x, y)$	$P^C = (u, v)$
0	0	0	0	1	(3885, 88200)	(111, -69615)
1	1	1	1	-1	(-4427535/1369, 6153669900/50653)	(111, 69615)
0	0	0	1	-1	(5355, 286650)	(-22, -3535)
1	1	1	0	1	(-465570/121, 18522000/1331)	(-22, 3535)
0	0	1	0	-1	(-3570, 88200)	(-102, 64575)
1	1	0	1	1	(1228395/289, 709061850/4913)	(-102, -64575)
0	0	1	0	0	(-315, -88200)	(1, 315)
1	1	0	1	0	(396585, -249738300)	(1, -315)
0	1	-1	1	-1	(4110, 124200)	(-294, -520065)
1	0	2	0	1	(-170085/49, 34428150/343)	(-294, 520065)
0	1	0	0	0	(105, -44100)	(3, 315)
1	0	1	1	0	(44205, -9261000)	(3, -315)
0	1	0	0	1	(-2765, 144550)	(36, 6615)
1	0	1	1	-1	(14665/4, 307475/8)	(36, -6615)
0	1	0	1	-1	(-1491, 144648)	(15, 945)
1	0	1	0	1	(3801, -72324)	(15, -945)
0	1	0	1	0	(-9135/4, -1223775/8)	(-4, 385)
1	0	1	0	0	(28035, 4652550)	(-4, -385)
0	1	1	0	-1	(4761, 211716)	(-35, -8295)
1	0	0	1	1	(-3771, 49608)	(-35, 8295)
0	1	1	0	0	(11235, -1124550)	(6, -315)
1	0	0	1	0	(210, 22050)	(6, 315)
0	0	1	0	1	(12105, 1268100)	(-7, -595)
1	0	0	1	-1	(-3195, -124200)	(-7, 595)
1	1	1	1	0	(-629, -109306)	(0, 315)
0	0	0	0	0	\mathcal{O}	(0, -315)

Table 3: All points $P^E = \sum_i m_i P_i^E$ with $P^C = (u, v) \in \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{Z}$.

We must also check the points $(x, y) \in E(\mathbb{Q})$ that are zeros of the polynomial $q(x) = x^2 - 630x - 13792275$ that appears in the denominator of $\mathcal{U}(x, y)$ and $\mathcal{V}(x, y)$. But the zeros of $q(x)$ are irrational, so we do not have any new solutions.

Finally, we come back to the collision equation $\binom{m}{2} = \binom{n}{8} + 1$ from which we started. We have $m = (v + 105)/210$, hence $105|v$, and $2u = n^2 - 7n + 12$. The only solutions (u, v) with v divisible by 105 are those listed in Table 4, where also the corresponding values of $(m, n) \in \mathbb{N}^2$ are listed.

(u, v)	$(m, n) \in \mathbb{N}^2$
(1, 315)	(2, 5), (2, 2)
(3, 315)	(2, 6), (2, 1)
(36, 6615)	(32, 12)
(15, 945)	(5, 9)
(6, 315)	(2, 0), (2, 7)
(0, 315)	(2, 4), (2, 3)

Table 4: Positive integer solutions of the collision equation $\binom{m}{2} = \binom{n}{8} + 1$

Note that no pair (m, n) in the above table satisfies the condition $m \geq 4$ and $n \geq 16$, therefore we have proved the following.

Corollary 3.2. *There is no (8, 2) near-collision with difference 1.*

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